

Mixed Model Analysis

[DataSet1] /Users/atom/Library/Mobile Documents/com~apple~CloudDocs/Desktop/PhD Docs/Main study/OWM_1.2.sav

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
	Doctor * Age_centered	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_w		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_w		
	Doctor * Age_centered		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	717.077520
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	729.077520
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	729.291806
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	759.011289
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	753.011289

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	204.724	1612.817	<.001
Patient	1	200.868	18623.863	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	203.553	.834	.362
Doctor * Communication_w	1	198.890	28.488	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	201.282	12.386	<.001
Patient * Communication_w	1	201.364	74.811	<.001
Doctor * Age_centered	1	198.534	4.159	.043

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.523	.113	204.724	40.160	<.001	4.301
Patient	4.631	.034	200.868	136.469	<.001	4.564
Doctor * Communication_b	.212	.232	203.553	.913	.362	-.246
Doctor * Communication_w	.707	.132	198.890	5.337	<.001	.446
Patient * Communication_b	.506	.144	201.282	3.519	<.001	.223
Patient * Communication_w	.554	.064	201.364	8.649	<.001	.428
Doctor * Age_centered	.015	.007	198.534	2.039	.043	.000

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.745
Patient	4.697
Doctor * Communication_t	.669
Doctor * Communication_v	.968
Patient * Communication_t	.790
Patient * Communication_v	.680
Doctor * Age_centered	.030

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.221	.022	9.973	<.001	.182
	Var(2)	.532	.053	9.978	<.001	.437
	Corr(2,1)	.306	.065	4.685	<.001	.173
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.
	Var(2)	.000	.000	.	.	.000
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.269
	Var(2)	.647
	Corr(2,1)	.428
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.
	Var(2)	.000
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
	Doctor * Age_centered	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
	Doctor * Age_centered		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	688.145909
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	700.145909
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	700.360195
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	730.079678
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	724.079678

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	17.705	919.231	<.001
Patient	1	182.909	16982.201	<.001
Doctor * Trust_b	1	19.387	2.365	.140
Doctor * Trust_w	1	193.717	86.224	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	191.695	17.207	<.001
Patient * Trust_w	1	198.986	48.046	<.001
Doctor * Age_centered	1	18.079	5.896	.026

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.620	.152	17.705	30.319	<.001	4.300
Patient	4.658	.036	182.909	130.316	<.001	4.587
Doctor * Trust_b	.513	.333	19.387	1.538	.140	-.184
Doctor * Trust_w	.666	.072	193.717	9.286	<.001	.525
Patient * Trust_b	.735	.177	191.695	4.148	<.001	.386
Patient * Trust_w	.504	.073	198.986	6.932	<.001	.361
Doctor * Age_centered	.024	.010	18.079	2.428	.026	.003

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.941
Patient	4.728
Doctor * Trust_b	1.209
Doctor * Trust_w	.808
Patient * Trust_b	1.085
Patient * Trust_w	.648
Doctor * Age_centered	.045

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.232	.023	9.903	<.001	.190
	Var(2)	.406	.042	9.628	<.001	.331
	Corr(2,1)	.272	.070	3.879	<.001	.130
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.041	.028	1.459	.144	.011
	Var(2)	.001	.004	.365	.715	6.880E-6
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.283
	Var(2)	.497
	Corr(2,1)	.403
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.157
	Var(2)	.314
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
	Doctor * education_centred	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
	Doctor * education_centred		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	687.667574
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	699.667574
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	699.881860
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	729.601343
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	723.601343

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	17.879	3528.747	<.001
Patient	1	199.761	18256.552	<.001
Doctor * Trust_b	1	22.418	3.683	.068
Doctor * Trust_w	1	192.763	82.545	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	199.579	17.784	<.001
Patient * Trust_w	1	199.819	50.362	<.001
Doctor * education_centred	1	189.817	1.640	.202

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.292	.072	17.879	59.403	<.001	4.140
Patient	4.656	.034	199.761	135.117	<.001	4.588
Doctor * Trust_b	.655	.341	22.418	1.919	.068	-.052
Doctor * Trust_w	.659	.073	192.763	9.085	<.001	.516
Patient * Trust_b	.724	.172	199.579	4.217	<.001	.386
Patient * Trust_w	.520	.073	199.819	7.097	<.001	.375
Doctor * education_centred	.064	.050	189.817	1.281	.202	-.035

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.444
Patient	4.724
Doctor * Trust_b	1.361
Doctor * Trust_w	.802
Patient * Trust_b	1.063
Patient * Trust_w	.664
Doctor * education_centred	.162

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.233	.023	9.960	<.001	.191
	Var(2)	.405	.042	9.649	<.001	.330
	Corr(2,1)	.270	.070	3.840	<.001	.128
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.049	.028	1.766	.077	.016
	Var(2)	2.089E-5	.000	.055	.956	8.905E-21
	Corr(2,1)	-1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% Confidence . Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.284
	Var(2)	.496
	Corr(2,1)	.402
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.150
	Var(2)	4.902E+10
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
	Doctor * education_centred	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_v		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_v		
	Doctor * education_centred		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	705.988112
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	717.988112
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	718.202397
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	747.921880
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	741.921880

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.992	3373.407	<.001
Patient	1	51.799	13729.503	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	20.327	.388	.540
Doctor * Communication_w	1	204.892	38.213	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	63.755	8.906	.004
Patient * Communication_w	1	200.283	76.374	<.001
Doctor * education_centred	1	194.752	3.499	.063

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.300	.074	16.992	58.081	<.001	4.144
Patient	4.619	.039	51.799	117.173	<.001	4.540
Doctor * Communication_b	.189	.303	20.327	.623	.540	-.442
Doctor * Communication_w	.815	.132	204.892	6.182	<.001	.555
Patient * Communication_b	.487	.163	63.755	2.984	.004	.161
Patient * Communication_w	.558	.064	200.283	8.739	<.001	.432
Doctor * education_centred	.101	.054	194.752	1.871	.063	-.006

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.456
Patient	4.698
Doctor * Communication_b	.819
Doctor * Communication_v	1.075
Patient * Communication_b	.812
Patient * Communication_v	.684
Doctor * education_centred	.208

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.214	.022	9.816	<.001	.175
	Var(2)	.488	.051	9.645	<.001	.398
	Corr(2,1)	.270	.068	3.943	<.001	.131
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.046	.032	1.452	.147	.012
	Var(2)	.007	.008	.874	.382	.001
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter	95% ...	
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.262
	Var(2)	.598
	Corr(2,1)	.398
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.178
	Var(2)	.066
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
	Doctor * Experience_centred	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_v		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_v		
	Doctor * Experience_centred		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	711.866002
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	723.866002
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	724.080287
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	753.799770
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	747.799770

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	14.556	3240.069	<.001
Patient	1	38.220	13079.624	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	17.724	.235	.634
Doctor * Communication_w	1	207.532	36.523	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	47.088	8.568	.005
Patient * Communication_w	1	200.408	73.845	<.001
Doctor * Experience_centred	1	53.992	.904	.346

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.299	.076	14.556	56.922	<.001	4.137
Patient	4.619	.040	38.220	114.366	<.001	4.537
Doctor * Communication_b	.151	.312	17.724	.485	.634	-.505
Doctor * Communication_w	.811	.134	207.532	6.043	<.001	.547
Patient * Communication_b	.488	.167	47.088	2.927	.005	.152
Patient * Communication_w	.551	.064	200.408	8.593	<.001	.424
Doctor * Experience_centred	.010	.010	53.992	.951	.346	-.011

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.460
Patient	4.700
Doctor * Communication_b	.807
Doctor * Communication_w	1.076
Patient * Communication_b	.823
Patient * Communication_w	.677
Doctor * Experience_centred	.031

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.214	.022	9.794	<.001	.175
	Var(2)	.493	.051	9.607	<.001	.402
	Corr(2,1)	.266	.069	3.864	<.001	.127
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.049	.036	1.375	.169	.012
	Var(2)	.008	.009	.898	.369	.001
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.261
	Var(2)	.604
	Corr(2,1)	.395
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.206
	Var(2)	.073
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
	Doctor * Experience_centred	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
	Doctor * Experience_centred		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	688.033153
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	700.033153
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	700.247439
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	729.966922
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	723.966922

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	14.364	3839.250	<.001
Patient	1	182.687	16940.958	<.001
Doctor * Trust_b	1	19.275	2.540	.127
Doctor * Trust_w	1	193.716	86.205	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	191.844	17.151	<.001
Patient * Trust_w	1	198.882	47.949	<.001
Doctor * Experience_centred	1	18.623	5.807	.026

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.289	.069	14.364	61.962	<.001	4.141
Patient	4.658	.036	182.687	130.157	<.001	4.587
Doctor * Trust_b	.532	.334	19.275	1.594	.127	-.166
Doctor * Trust_w	.666	.072	193.716	9.285	<.001	.525
Patient * Trust_b	.734	.177	191.844	4.141	<.001	.385
Patient * Trust_w	.504	.073	198.882	6.925	<.001	.360
Doctor * Experience_centred	.026	.011	18.623	2.410	.026	.003

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.437
Patient	4.728
Doctor * Trust_b	1.231
Doctor * Trust_w	.808
Patient * Trust_b	1.084
Patient * Trust_w	.647
Doctor * Experience_centred	.049

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.232	.023	9.901	<.001	.190
	Var(2)	.406	.042	9.631	<.001	.331
	Corr(2,1)	.272	.070	3.888	<.001	.130
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.042	.028	1.484	.138	.011
	Var(2)	.002	.004	.376	.707	8.240E-6
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.283
	Var(2)	.497
	Corr(2,1)	.403
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.158
	Var(2)	.281
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.